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Review Article

ADVOCACY OF PHARMACIST TOWARDS CONCOMITANT SOCIAL MEDIA: MEETING AN URGE TO PATIENTS NEED & OUTCOME

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Received: 12 October 2016**Accepted:** 28 December 2016**Published:** 31 January 2017**Abstract:**

In the modern era, technology has taken a radical avant-garde towards social media. It is presently being used as a stature household need by every mankind. The revolutionary of social media has brought a dynamic impact in networking health information between the professional and patient, irrespective of age group. This laid a "bleeding-heart" platform for pharmacist, escalating the utilization by improving the health outcomes and meeting the urge. There is a vague informative literature around this upcoming subject. To bridge this gap, the authors reconnoitre the positive potential areas concentrating on the use and applications of social media by pharmacist to improvise & reinvigorate determinants of health outcomes. The subject was extensively studied in five main modules. 1. Encapsulating the complete medical information 2. Innocuous usage of medicine 3. In perpetuity medication usage 4. Document based medicine & implementation guidelines & 5. Clinical inquisition. In each of these perceptive modules, an increase in manoeuvre & habitude of social media platforms by pharmacists & other health care professionals have brought a great impact and changeover in improving patients need and outcome. In this busy competitive world, most of the young generation (≤ 35 years) are falling in the usage of upgraded and popular social media, leaving behind the majority of old group. However, the majority of patients fall in the category of old generation (≥ 50 years), and the usage of this type of platforms will definitely stabilise and improve the health outcomes in the nearby future.

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INTRODUCTION:

Social media has taken a big leap in continuum growth both in popularity and practice [1]. This clearly suggests, for long time sustainability. It has surpassed so once called phone calls, mails, fax & personal communication. In today modern world, the interpersonal communication like instant messages, tweets, sharing videos, posts, photographs have taken an edge growth. Social skinny [2], O'Hara [3] & Eckler PE [4] et al., clearly delineated the important augmentation stating the raise of "e-society", influencing the development of healthcare landscape.

The most vital key factor in today "e-revolution" is usage of social media at doorstep itself, in form of

smart android gadgets. Intensifying this progress growth, the health care professional like a pharmacist must prepare oneself, in serving the community and ensuring the patient health care management [5-8]. This strategy must further develop engaging the patients by guiding and advising the positive impact on health outcomes. But without the two key actions i.e sharing and socialization, the social media would have taken a back step. To overcome the two key actions there are surfeit of social media sites and various apps, extending a helping hand for accuracy of health care outcomes as described in Table: 1.

Table 1: Social Media Types & Health Site Related Examples

Type	Definition	Example	Health related examples (not endorsed or recommended)
Blog	Online journal or diary where authors share stories, views or opinions	www.blogger.com www.wordpress.org www.tumblr.com	www.health.org www.healthylivingblogs.com www.patient.co.in/blogs www.healthcareblog.com www.healthline.com www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov Helps in understanding every outcome and enabling individual to understand the disease
Micro blog	Similar to blog but posts are much shorter and contemporary	www.twitter.com www.posterous.com www.friendfeed.com www.plurk.com	All most all health organisations, bodies, and leading personalities will have a twitter account www.moodmill.com www.googlehealth.com
Social networks	Online communities that share interest or activities through profiles which link together	www.facebook.com www.twitter.com www.linkedin.com www.pinterest.com www.googleplus.com www.myspace.com	www.patientslikeme.com www.connectedliving.com www.curediva.com www.informationweek.com These helps in profile outline understanding the need and emergency in patient outcome
Photo/video/file sharing sites	Sharing of digital media related to healthcare	www.youtube.com www.youku.com www.dailymotion.com www.vimeo.com	Many organisations have their own channels of presentations and sharing and hosting videos
Instant messaging/ contacts	Websites or app that allows easy instant messages, calls, photographs, sharing locations to individual or groups	www.whatsapp.com www.viber.com www.wechat.com www.line.com www.kakaotalk.com www.kik.com	These apps helps in sending emergency health related care at instant and much useful in present techno world

Table 2: Summary Of Data On Social Media Activity Reported In 2016

EXAMPLES OF SOCIAL MEDIA	DATA ON ACTIVITY
Facebook	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● 1.71 billion users ● 39% of Facebook users check their accounts more than five times a day ● 79% of possible engagement with a post gets it in the first 3 hours ● 19% of users do not use privacy settings
Twitter	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Over 570 million users with 303 million active users monthly ● 71% of users access it from mobile device ● 501 million tweets per day ● Fastest growing age demographic is aged between 40-70 years
Google plus	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● 527 million users in the platform and out of which 64% male the 36% female ● 71% users log in everyday
LinkedIn	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● 450 million users with 3.1 million groups ● 4.3 million businesses have pages ● 70% of users have degree
YouTube	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● 60 hours of video are uploaded every minute ● Over 4 billion videos are viewed a day. ● Over 800 million unique users visit each month. ● Over 3 billion hours of video are watched each month on YouTube.

STATISTIC ANALYSIS:

A soaring rise in riposte usage of social media, within the users is highly “eye-popping”. Majority usage and engagement data provided a profound insight into transition and innovative transformations with social media. Table: 2 provide a summary of data on social media activity reported in 2016 [9,10]. A recent study has been envisaged, indicating the majority of young generation are using smart phones and higher versions of android gadgets, searching online for health care advices [11-13] and information. The trend of inflation usage of internet laid a cornerstone in precision and accuracy of health data information [14-20].

PHARMACIST – SOCIAL MEDIA MANAGEMENT:

There are no clear documentation reports of pharmacists, using social media. Sheherbakova et al [21] surveyed pharmacists in Texas, USA and reported, less usage of online search for health information. They reportedly framed the purpose of extensive use of social media for a good cause of health management, which can be useful to communicate with patients. Cains et al [22] studied the data analysis of students using social media, in search of database of health care system, promoting products and services rendered. As the “e-society” is growing, it appears, the key role play of pharmacists [23] can enhance patient care, practice

and health outcomes. This review article promotes the role of pharmacist bringing an impact and change in patient recuperation [24].

PURSUIT DESIGN/STRATEGY

Many search engines like Google, MSN search, Bing, Yahoo, AOL search, PubMed, Scopus, Google scholar, Embase etc were thoroughly scrutinized using the terminology “social media/networking, pharmacist, patient’s outcome and impact”. To a great bewilderment and review, there was neither of the concern findings. In view of “hawkeye” to the context, the authors extended, to include a relevant discussion to bolster and patch up the need, by toasting a raise in professional health care team for betterment of health outcomes.

PROSPECTIVE CHALLENGES FOR PHARMACIST:

A broad summative of “stone’s throw” challenges are very much promising for pharmacist in adapting his or her role in bringing out new dimensional manifestation in patients health care. The core objective challenge is the role module, in usage of health care management with social media. This apt, provoke a great ultimatum challenges, to the concerned pharmacist. The literature is very much finite. The pharmacist must obligate to track the fickle nature of social media trends very frequently. The other quite challenge on

operative aspect is that, social network is a complete public domain. It's absolutely difficult to manage the health care patient management due to lack of undocked privacy. Pharmacy professionals should consider another alternative methodology, if patients couldn't manage or refused to access information through social media networking [25]. In contradictory, the patient data shouldn't be problematic, if much of the contact details were constructive. The another concerned twirl, regarding social networking is about online accuracy and appropriateness, leading to patients mental stress and strain, taking abrupt decisions regarding health, including self medication and non adherence [26-28]. To overcome the retardation of patient health, the pharmacist should play a vital role in promotion of evidence based information to patients in a reliable manner. The final point of inquest lies within the pharmacists. The difference in generation gap should be sorted and well executed, by employing significant training and hands on experience. It should be expected that concerned regulators, provide further guidance, as social networking permeates health care management.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION:

The literature "amass" for the key role of pharmacist yielded a very much defined number of papers. Most of the other related papers broadened their extensive studies on usage of social media, in educational institutes and on general professionalism. Various proposed modules/themes as shown in Table: 3 were identified using social media to improve health outcomes. It is clear that there are very limited, high quality data or well-structured studies, towards social media and impact on health outcomes. This is probably, due to the difficulty in designed studies, which could clearly determine the unique impact of social media, coupled with the relative newness of social media and the rapidly changing social media environment.

Table 3: Summary of Proposed Areas Where Social Media Could Be Used By Pharmacist to Improve Health Outcomes

Sr. No	PROPOSED MODULE
1.	Encapsulating the complete medical information
2.	Innocuous usage of medicine
3.	In perpetuity medication usage
4.	Document based medicine & implementation guidelines
5.	Clinical inquisition

From the above table, the pharmacist with social media can bring new dimensions, communicating

health information to patients with relevant interactions raising the quality and reliability [29] of the accurate data by posting on social networking domains with patient privacy considerations. Health care interventions through internet can show a great promising field in reaching patient group of all ages. An interesting point in the nearby future for all health care professionals specify, the great usage of patient online or digital intervention to be more positive. Guse et al [30] claim that there is tremendous potential in the fields of medicine and health to reach young populations, but suggested that more research is required to address the potential inequalities with regard to access to digital parameters in the lower socioeconomic groups. Social media may offer promising field in supporting patients who find it difficult to engage in traditional face-to-face peer support groups, such as those with mental disabilities. Merchant et al [31] proposed a little retrospective evidence, with the potential value of social media in public emergencies and crisis management, by analyzing the handling and utilization of the social networking by pharmacist. Direct online health professional services are emerging, where the patient can request online diagnosis and treatment through various web portals [32]. These provide timely diagnosis & treatment for clear-cut illness by professional health care team to improve patient's outcome. Indeed there is a great potential for pharmacists to engage with social media in a novel way to encourage patients and to adhere with their medicine regimens by sharing information or any other health care related topics, at relevant times in a "tailored way" for the management of one's disease.

Merolli et al [33] also took an interest in usage of social media studying the influences of outcomes and analyzing the affordances of patients control over how they present and assert themselves. It also provides flexibility in regard to timing and location of communication about their health, which may challenge traditional health care delivery models. With the permeation of social media into all aspects of life, it is reasonable to assume that it could be used to have an impact on dissemination and implementation of evidence-based medicine and guidelines. Allen et al [34] looked at how social media could increase the dissemination on clinical pain services and concluded that social media enhances education and learning by improving the implementation of evidence based use of medicine [35-37]. Social media has been proposed to improve collegiality in learning environment. The broader application of social media in clinical trials has also been successful in enhancing patient recruitment and retention across a number of therapy areas. Social media provides significant opportunities and challenges by enhancing clinical

inquisition [38-40]. Another key factor is to bring great changes in posting clinical discussions and raising a commemoration in health forums.

CONCLUSION:

Social media can be employed as a “hodgepodge” platform in health care assessment by analyzing and defining a reciprocal discussion and engagement with patients. This can be a great driven force, showing promising results to every patient for a better living. The rapprochement of pharmacist should outline his or her conscience in an enhanced knowledge, with positive diversity and novelty interacting with patients. With these increased measurable outcomes, the social media can be a forefront runner in health care system. Mediation should be a primary resource, protecting the patient’s privacy from root level; else the whole constructive ideology can become a great disaster. Finally, based on the current evidence, the pharmacist pivotal role with social media can achieve better outcomes for patient’s health care management.

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